

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP5 – Data Workflow Implementation & Service Deployment

D5.2 Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures

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V1.1	12-01-2021	Final Version after consortium review

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Belgium
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This report provides an overview of the quality assurance and control procedures for the data workflow from source data to reliable evidence that have been developed and are being implemented in the EHDEN ecosystem. The focus is on the quality control mechanisms for the mapping of the source data to the CDM by the data partners and certified Small to Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs). It is highly important that these mappings are done using a fully transparent approach. To trust in the evidence generated there must be assurance that each step in the pipeline has been evaluated and examined. In this document we walk through how source data is transformed to the CDM, describing the tools employed along the way and how they contribute to the overall quality assurance of the data. In addition, we briefly share insight on the quality control procedures of the analytical step taking the Health Analytics Data-to-Evidence Suite (HADES) as an example.

This work is part of Task 5.1 “Implementation of Quality Assurance and Control Procedures” which runs till the end of the project. We will use the learnings from all WPs in the remainder of the project to further extend the procedures and tools discussed in the current deliverable.

1. INTRODUCTION

The vision of the EHDEN project is to be the trusted observational research ecosystem to enable better health decisions, outcomes, and care by generating reliable evidence. We are implementing this vision through our work on standardization of a large amount of data sources to the OMOP CDM, the development of analytical tools, and the implementation of procedures for the execution of studies on the federated data network.

Reliable evidence has a number of desired attributes as also shown in Figure 1:

- **Repeatable** evidence is obtained when all elements, namely the question, researcher, data, and analysis are held constant and the same result is produced. This seems obvious and easy to obtain but proves to be challenging when common version-controlled analytic code cannot be applied.
- **Reproducible** evidence produces identical results when all elements are constant except the researcher. This requires that all the steps in the process are fully documented and all analytical steps are performed fully automatically.
- **Replicable** evidence combines the same question and analysis with similar data to achieve similar results. For this it crucial to understand whether differences in the results are only due to the differences in data and not because of the implementation of the analysis. For example, if we share a protocol or even a statistical analysis plan, but not analysis code, with data partners in our network, we cannot be sure they implement the analysis in the same way.
- **Generalizable** evidence takes the same question and analysis and produces similar results on different data. For example, if a prediction model transports well to another setting this would strengthen our belief that this model is reliable.
- **Robust evidence** is achieved when the same question approached with a different analysis gives similar results. This desired attribute can only be obtained if we have tools that can be parameterized and can be run on a large number of databases. If the conclusion of the study is consistent over different analysis settings this would improve our trust in the generated evidence.
- **Calibrated** evidence is achieved when similar questions answered by the same researcher on the same data with the same analysis produce statistically consistent results. This for example applies to effect estimation where negative controls are included to perform p-value calibration.

Desired attribute	Question	Researcher	Data	Analysis	Result
Repeatable	Identical	Identical	Identical	Identical	= Identical
Reproducible	Identical	Different	Identical	Identical	= Identical
Replicable	Identical	Same or different	Similar	Identical	= Similar
Generalizable	Identical	Same or different	Different	Identical	= Similar
Robust	Identical	Same or different	Same or different	Different	= Similar
Calibrated	Similar (controls)	Identical	Identical	Identical	= Statistically consistent

Figure 1. Desired attributes of the evidence we generate

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Reliable evidence can be achieved through common analytics which requires both structural i.e., tables and fields, and *semantic* (alignment on a shared vocabulary) data standardization. As shown in Figure 2 below, we are effectively splitting up the journey from source data to reliable evidence in: 1) data standardization, 2) analysis execution.

Figure 2. Pipeline for creating reliable evidence through the use of the CDM

Proper quality control mechanisms need to be in place throughout this pipeline and especially in the data standardization part of the process. For this we can identify multiple steps as shown in Figure 3 .

Figure 3: The data conversion to analysis pipeline

- Starting with the data in the source schema the WhiteRabbit tool produces a scan that shows the values that are present in the data rather than relying on often incorrect or incomplete source data dictionaries.
- The ETL design and implementation, supported by the Rabbit-In-a-Hat tool, needs to be fully transparent and should not result in loss of valuable information.
- In parallel the source codes need to be mapped to the standardized vocabularies for example by using the Usagi tool. These vocabularies are being updated over time and it is important to understand the changes and their impact on the ETL. This could for example be domain changes which are very important for analysis since concept domains tell the analytic packages where to look for records. The Tantalus tool offers functionality to assess the changes between two versions of the vocabulary.

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- Once the data is available in the CDM format, the Data Quality Dashboard and Achilles characterization applications test the conformance to data standards and check for unexpected anomalies in the data. This process is supported by a new R package called CdmInspection that fully automatically generates an inspection report.
- Finally, when the data are ready for analysis, there is a suite of tools and best practice approaches to make sure the proper questions are asked, that the software does what it is supposed to do, and that the correct study design has been chosen.

In the upcoming sections we will provide more details on each of these steps.

2. DATA STANDARDIZATION QUALITY CONTROL

As shown in Figure 3 above, the process to convert source data to the OMOP CDM has many steps and each one offers an opportunity for quality control and assurance. The tools WhiteRabbit and Rabbit-In-A-Hat facilitate the structural standardization of data by first revealing what tables and fields are available in a source data set (WhiteRabbit) and then mapping the source tables and fields to those in the CDM (Rabbit-In-A-Hat). These tools are maintained by EHDEN and used by the global OHDSI community. The semantic standardization is achieved by utilizing existing translations for common vocabularies (ICD10, Read, etc.) and by use of the Usagi tool that suggests potential standard concept mappings for source codes that are not already represented in the OMOP Vocabularies. Once the standardization is complete, the entire CDM is assessed for adherence to the Common Data Model standards through the of Data Quality Dashboard. Each of these tools is managed using a git version control system. The exact process depends on the application, but new versions are documented and tested prior to release and communicated to SMEs through the combination of the EHDEN academy, EHDEN forums, and trainings. Further description of these tools and their contribution to the overall quality assessment of a source-to-CDM transformation is discussed below.

2.1 Summarize the Source Data

Figure 4: Summarize the source data with WhiteRabbit

Step 1 is to summarize the data that will be converted to the OMOP CDM. While many Data Partners provide a data dictionary to describe each table and field and the allowable values, it is our experience that these are often incorrect or incomplete. The WhiteRabbit¹ tool scans the data and provides a report containing all information necessary to begin designing the ETL.

White Rabbit’s main function is to perform a scan of the source data, providing detailed information on the tables, fields, and values that appear in a field. The source data can be in comma-separated text files, or in a database (MySQL, SQL Server, Oracle, PostgreSQL, Microsoft APS, Microsoft Access, Amazon RedShift). The scan will generate a report that can be used as a reference when designing the ETL, for instance by using it in conjunction with the Rabbit-In-a-Hat tool. White Rabbit differs from standard data profiling tools in that it attempts to prevent the display of personally identifiable information (PII) data values in the generated

¹ <https://ohdsi.github.io/WhiteRabbit/WhiteRabbit.html>

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output data file. Once the scan is complete, an Excel file is generated with one tab present for each table scanned as well as an overview tab. The overview tab lists all tables scanned, fields in each table, the data type of each field, the maximum length of the field, the number of rows in the table, the number of rows scanned, and how often each field was found to be empty. The report is the first step in quality assurance by highlighting what exists in a database. Rather than relying on the data dictionary to understand what *should* be present the scan gives a report on what is present. This exposes issues up front, allowing the conversion step to address them and eliminating rework during mapping.

A great example is the listed sex at birth for a person. Often data dictionaries list the allowable values as M,F or 1,2. Just as often the WhiteRabbit scan report shows a small number of persons with either a NULL or “Unknown” value. Use of the scan report rather than the data dictionary makes the certified Small to Medium-sized Enterprise or Data Partner aware of the issue at the outset so that they might build a solution into the OMOP CDM transformation. The White Rabbit tool thus initiates valuable discussions with the Data Partner to understand their data better.

2.2 Vocabulary Quality Processes

Figure 5: The OMOP vocabulary pipeline

The full detailed description of the vocabulary quality control process will be part of an upcoming deliverable in WP4. Here a high level overview is given.

Athena provides curated standardized vocabularies. They serve two major purposes: a) providing specific standard concepts that will be used as target concepts in the ETL process to build an OMOP CDM and b) a multitude of vocabularies representing source data in many different healthcare data (such as ICD coding) to allow mapping from those non-standard concepts to the above-mentioned standard ones. The process for creating those standardized vocabularies consists of ingesting source files into the vocabulary database to prepare a transformation into the OMOP vocabulary format, translation if the source is non-English and a consecutive mapping step to standard concepts. The mapping is the most complex and time-consuming step and requires automatic as well as manual processes.

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Figure 6. Process to add new vocabularies

The Quality Assurance process for the mappings is again done based on scripted consistency checks as well as manual review following a 4 eyes principle as described in Figure 7.

- Automatic and manual QA on the input tables of the process (stage tables)
- Automatic checks when moving from stage tables to concept tables
- Automatic checks within release process, creation of release notes

Figure 7. Quality Control Process for Vocabularies

Once a vocabulary has gone through Quality Control, it is released to the Athena Platform and can be downloaded for use in the local OMOP environment.

After downloading from ATHENA² the vocabulary should be examined in two ways. The first is to evaluate the vocabulary in relation to the native data. We have seen with many Data Partners that often European datasets are coded using either country or site-specific codes. In the case that source codes are not represented in the OMOP Vocabulary they must be mapped to Standard Concepts using the Usagi³ tool. Without this step there is a risk that data captured using site-specific codes would not be recognized or included in the standard analytic processes. The Usagi application facilitates the manual mapping of source

² <https://athena.ohdsi.org/search-terms/start>

³ <https://github.com/ohdsi/usagi>

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codes to Standard Concepts by using concept names and synonyms to find potential matches. A potential risk at this point is that a wrong mapping will be made. To mitigate that risk all mappings are reviewed by the data owners and clinical experts to ensure they are correct. Usagi then exports the results in a format that is easy to use during the ETL.

The second way to evaluate the ATHENA download is to compare it to a prior version of the vocabulary. This usually happens in the course of regular maintenance and CDM updates. The vocabulary updates often and it is good practice to stay current, within three months of the latest release. One risk associated with vocabulary changes is the domain movement of concepts. The domain of a concept dictates what table the record belongs in. For example, a concept in the ‘Drug’ domain will land that record in the DRUG_EXPOSURE table. Similarly, a concept in the ‘Condition’ domain will put the record in the CONDITION_OCCURRENCE table. When an analytical package is designed it leverages these rules to look for records in the tables specified by their domains. However, if a concept moves domains but the analyst is not aware of the movement, the package may still look in the old location for a concept. It is imperative to understand these domain movements not only for data model compliance but when adapting studies that were built using older vocabulary versions. In this case the Tantalus⁴ tool is used to expose the differences between two vocabularies. It exposes many changes, like changes to a concept’s name, concepts that have been added to the vocabulary, and source concepts that have new mappings to standard concepts. To narrow down the changes that are most important in relation to a single dataset it also reports back the prevalence of each concept that has a change. For instance, if a concept moves from the ‘Condition’ domain to the ‘Observation’ domain but that concept is never used in the database of interest then it can be filtered out. In this way the results are tailored to the database and noise is filtered out. The ETL developer is then able to take any action necessary to inform analysts of changes in the vocabulary that directly impact their studies.

2.3 Creating and Implementing the ETL Design

Figure 6: ETL design and implementation

After scanning a database with Usagi, the ETL design and vocabulary steps are often performed in concert. To facilitate the CDM conversion the Rabbit-In-a-Hat⁵ tool reads and displays a White Rabbit scan report. White Rabbit generates information about the source data while Rabbit-In-a-Hat uses that information and, through a graphical user interface, allows a user to connect source data to tables and columns within the CDM. Rabbit-In-a-Hat then generates documentation for the extract, transform, and load (ETL) process and guidelines for how the implementation code should be written.

This is a very important quality assurance step. It is imperative that the code implemented to convert data from the source structure to the OMOP CDM follow the rules laid out in the ETL document and is following the agreed conventions. There are multiple ways this can be achieved, enumerated as follows:

⁴ <https://github.com/ohdsi/tantalus>

⁵ <https://ohdsi.github.io/WhiteRabbit/RabbitInAHat.html>

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1. Review of the ETL design document, computer code, and code mappings. Any one person can make mistakes, so at least one other person always reviews what was done.
2. Unit tests are used to replicate a pattern in the source data that should be addressed in the ETL. For example, if the ETL specifies that patients without gender information should be dropped, a unit test of a person without a gender is created and the code is assessed for how it handles that specific situation. These unit tests should be run whenever the ETL code is updated. For more information see the testing framework as described on the Rabbit in a Hat documentation.⁶
 - a. This approach usually involves creating a much smaller dataset that mimics the structure of the source data being converted. Each person or record in the dataset tests a specific piece of logic as written in the ETL document. Using this method, it is easy to trace back issues and to identify failing logic. The small size also enables the computer code to execute very quickly allowing for faster iterations and error identification.
3. Overall counts between the source data and converted data are compared. This helps to pinpoint if any data is unexpectedly dropped during the transformation process or if a cartesian product is produced.
 - a. There may be some expected difference in counts depending on how the ETL and code handle certain issues (like dropping people without a gender).

2.4 Perform Quality Assessment

Figure 7: Data quality assessment procedures

Once the source data are converted to the OMOP CDM, there are two tools employed to interrogate the quality of the both the conversion to the Common Data Model and the data itself. The first of these is the Data Quality Dashboard⁶ (DQD), described fully in deliverable 4.2. This tool uses a systematic approach to run and evaluate over 3,300 data quality checks against a given CDM instance, as seen in figure 8. It aligns with the Kahn data quality categories of conformance, completeness, and plausibility to assess how well a dataset conforms with OMOP and OHDSI standards, how well source codes are mapped to standard concepts, and the plausibility of certain data values. This has proven to be an invaluable tool along the pipeline by identifying multiple issues (which are subsequently addressed) as well as providing further education to both SMEs and Data Partners on data standards and expectations.

⁶ <https://ohdsi.github.io/DataQualityDashboard/index.html>

DATA QUALITY ASSESSMENT

SYNTHA

DataQualityDashboard Version: 1.0.0
Results generated at 2020-09-09 09:37:37 in 14 mins

	Verification				Validation				Total			
	Pass	Fail	Total	% Pass	Pass	Fail	Total	% Pass	Pass	Fail	Total	% Pass
Plausibility	1870	8	1878	100%	287	0	287	100%	2157	8	2165	100%
Conformance	672	9	681	99%	104	0	104	100%	776	9	785	99%
Completeness	383	3	386	99%	15	0	15	100%	398	3	401	99%
Total	2925	20	2945	99%	406	0	406	100%	3331	20	3351	99%

Figure 8: The overview of the Data Quality Dashboard

After a CDM instance is evaluated by the DQD and any issues are fixed, the ACHILLES tool is then run to provide a characterization of the entire database. ACHILLES precomputes over 170 characterizations and displays them in an application called ACHILLESWeb to allow exploration and identification of potential quality issues. For example, figure 9 shows the data density plot which displays the number of records in each table over time. Most of the data starts in 2005 but there are some records from 1961, which is likely an error in the data.

Figure 9: The data density plot in the ACHILLES web browser

The Data Quality Dashboard is described in depth in D4.6 “Final version of the framework for quality benchmarking.

2.5 Inspection Report

Once the source data have been converted to the CDM and all steps followed, each data partner must also complete an inspection report. The goal of the inspection report is to provide insight into the completeness, transparency and quality of the performed Extraction Transform, and Load (ETL) process and the readiness of the data partner to be onboarded in the EHDEN and OHDSI data networks and participate in research studies. All ETL documentation is shared including the vocabulary mapping process, the status of the ETL code, the Data Quality Dashboard results, and maintenance plans. ETL code must be versioned to enable the

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reproducibility of the CDM. As part of the inspection task performed by a certified SME, the CdmInspection⁷ package must be executed which performs a number of queries meant to check the performance and compliance of the system. It also verifies that the data partner has the appropriate software installed to participate in network research. The template work document is generated fully automatically from the CDM and has placeholder for parts that require input from the Data Custodian and the SME. An example of the inspection report is listed in Annex 1 and is generated against a simulated database. The inspection report provides an additional quality control check and contains additional value on top of the Data Quality Dashboard and signs of all the steps that are necessary for a data partner to be included in the network. It is an important step in the workplan that is part of the sub-grant agreement and will be reviewed by the EHDEN taskforce before initiating a milestone payment.

2.5 ANALYTICAL PIPELINE QUALITY ASSURANCE

Figure 10. The approach to execute the analytical steps.

The Book of OHDSI⁸ describes the measures in place developed by OHDSI in conjunction with EHDEN to assess clinical validity, software validity, and method validity. Clinical validity begins with the cohort that has been defined to answer the specific clinical question. Once it is defined it is evaluated using cohort diagnostics⁹. The OHDSI Cohort Diagnostics tool creates descriptive results for each candidate phenotype such as the characteristics of the patients identified by the phenotype, the validity of the code sets and the number of patients identified by the phenotype across calendar time. This is repeated across the OHDSI network of databases. The results are then inspected by a clinician to compare the characteristics of the patients identified by the phenotype, the temporal trend of the phenotype and the number of patients identified by the phenotype across numerous databases. The specific aspects of a phenotype that are inspected are:

- Generalizability. Do the patients captured by the phenotype appear to represent the real-world patients with the illness? This requires inspecting the characteristics of the patients identified by the phenotype.

⁷ <https://github.com/EHDEN/CdmInspection>

⁸ <https://ohdsi.github.io/TheBookOfOhdsi/ClinicalValidity.html>

⁹ <https://ohdsi.github.io/CohortDiagnostics/>

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- Consistency across the network. Is the phenotype identifying patients consistently across the network or does it seem to fail for one or more database? This may indicate an issue with the transportability of the definition. Common issues include unsuitable data or incorrect code sets.
- Correctness of concept sets (code sets). Do we have correct codes for identifying inclusion/exclusion criteria used by the phenotype? OHDSI use string similarity and associations to identify potential missing codes.

If issues are identified with a candidate phenotype then revisions to the phenotype are made and the process is repeated until no issues are observed.

Software validity is an essential component of evidence quality: only if our analysis software does what it is expected to do can we produce reliable evidence. This is done through automation, programming best practices, code validation, and use of the methods library. Traditionally, observational studies are often viewed as a journey rather than a process: a database expert may extract a data set from the database and hand this over to the data analyst, who may open it in a spreadsheet editor or other interactive tool, and start working on the analysis. In the end, a result is produced, but little is preserved of how it came about. This practice is entirely unacceptable, both because it is not reproducible, and also because it lacks transparency: we do not know exactly what was done to produce the result, so we cannot verify that no mistakes were made. Every analysis generating evidence must therefore be fully automated. By automated we mean the analysis should be implemented as a single script, and we should be able to redo the entire analysis from database in CDM format to results, including tables and figures, with a single command. The analysis can be of arbitrary complexity, perhaps producing just a single count, or generating empirically calibrated estimates for millions of research questions, but the same principle applies. The script can invoke other scripts, which in turn can invoke even lower-level analysis processes. Coding best practices are described in section [17.1.2](#) of [The Book of OHDSI](#) and include abstraction of code into discrete functions and clear naming of variables. This code is then validated most often by an independent person who reviews it. The OHDSI Methods Library provides a large set of functions, allowing most observational studies to be implemented using only a few lines of code. Using the Methods Library therefore shifts most of the burden of establishing the validity of one's study code to the Library. Validity of the Methods Library is ensured by its software development process and by extensive testing.

Method validity aims to understand if the proper study design has been chosen in relation to the clinical question of interest. "Method" includes not only the study design, but also the data and the implementation of the design. Method validity is therefore somewhat of a catch-all; it is often not possible to observe good method validity without good data quality, clinical validity, and software validity. Those aspects of evidence quality should have already been addressed separately before we consider method validity.

The core activity when establishing method validity is evaluating whether important assumptions in the analysis have been met. For example, we assume that propensity-score matching makes two populations comparable, but we need to evaluate whether this is the case. Where possible, empirical tests should be performed to verify these assumptions. We can for example generate diagnostics to show that our two populations are indeed comparable on a wide range of characteristics after matching. In OHDSI and EHDEN we have developed many standardized diagnostics that should be generated and evaluated whenever an analysis is performed. These range from design-specific diagnostics to diagnostics that should be run for all comparative effectiveness studies.

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3. CONCLUSION

The quality assurance pipeline described in this deliverable represents our current approaches to ensure data and evidence quality. Some have been the practice for many years, such as the use of WhiteRabbit and Rabbit-In-a-Hat to scan a dataset and map it to the Common Data Model, and are further developed. Others are relatively new; the CohortDiagnostics package was developed in 2020 and continues to evolve with more time and research, or developed recently by EHDEN, e.g., the Cdmlnspection package. Over the course of the EHDEN project (and beyond) this pipeline will be consistently evaluated through an iterative process with feedback loops to apply current learnings to future situations. This will include a focus on quality control on the tools themselves. In the upcoming project year, we will apply the approaches in the mapping exercises with the data partners and SME and will work on several publications to share our findings. This will include the planned federated study execution which will enable us to assess the effects of improved quality assurance measures on study results.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1 Inspection report template example

CDM Inspection report for the Medicare Claims Synthetic Public Use Files database

Package Version: 0.0.0.9000

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Authors: <NAME>

	D5.2 – Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures		
	WP5 – Data Workflow Implementation & Service Deployment		Version: v1.1 – Final
	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 19/48

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GENERAL INFORMATION

The goal of the inspection report is to provide insight into the completeness, transparency and quality of the performed Extraction Transform, and Load (ETL) process and the readiness of the data source to be onboarded in the data network to participate in research studies.

Contact Details

Fill in the table below

items	answers
Data Partner	
Database fullname	Medicare Claims Synthetic Public Use Files
Database acronym	SYNPUF
Contact Person	
Email	
SME	
Contact Person	
Email SME	

Database Description

The CMS Linkable 2008–2010 Medicare DE-SynPUF originated from a disjoint (mutually exclusive from existing samples) 5% random sample of beneficiaries from the 100% Beneficiary Summary File for 2008. To exclude any overlap with the beneficiaries in the existing 5% CMS research sample, 3 the beneficiaries in that other sample were excluded, and a 5-in-95 random draw was made with the remaining 95% of beneficiaries. A variety of statistical disclosure limitation techniques were used to protect the confidentiality of Medicare beneficiaries in the CMS Linkable 2008–2010 Medicare DE-SynPUF. The DE-SynPUF was created by starting with an actual beneficiary as a “seed” for a synthetic beneficiary. Synthetic beneficiaries and their claims are based on actual seed beneficiaries. Disclosure is reduced through multiple deterministically or stochastically applied treatment mechanisms. First, hot decking based procedures are used to find donors for beneficiary-level variables and individual claims. Second, other synthetic processes are used to protect other elements of the data. Disclosure limitation methods used in the process include variable reduction, suppression, substitution, synthesis, date perturbation, and coarsening. Please refer to the CMS Linkable 2008–2010 Medicare Data Entrepreneurs’ Synthetic Public Use File (DE-SynPUF) User Manual for details regarding how DE-SynPUF was created

SME Role

Describe the involvement of the SME in the ETL Delopment process

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ETL DEVELOPMENT GENERAL

This section describes the ETL development steps and discusses the quality control steps performed by the SME

ETL Documentation

Perform the following checks and discuss the findings here:

Approve the quality of the ETL documentation with respect to its completeness and level of detail per data domain. Ideally it is based on the Rabbit-in-a-Hat mapping definition document. If a staging table approach is used, its creation needs to be described in detail.

Does it contain enough detail on the applied business rules and are the THEMIS rules followed?

Compare the ETL documentation with the shared ETL code to make sure it is a correct representation of the implementation. Ideally, end-to-end tests using the Rabbit-in-a-hat testFramework.R is implemented and results are shared. If this is not available explain the quality control mechanism that is applied

Is the ETL code executable fully automatically or are there manual steps? If there are manual steps these need to be explained.

ETL Implementation

Described the technology used for implementing the ETL (SQL,R, Python etc).

Provide feedback on the level of commenting and code structure. The minimum level of commenting contains an explanation of the sql query, R function, etc. See also the guidance provided by OHDSI. Code structure refers to a logical structure of the SQL/R files. We recommend that the files are name as their target table and contain all code related to that domain, e.g. insert_person.sql, insert_condition_occurrence.sql. If another method is applied provide there details.

Is there a version control mechanism in place?

Record counts data tables

Table 1. Shows the number of records in all clinical data tables

TABLERNAME	COUNT
care_site	239,153
condition occurrence	14,803,406
condition_era	10,150,726
cost	37,169,949
death	5,461
device_exposure	224,499
dose_era	0
drug exposure	6,294,108
drug_era	6,251,166
drug_exposure	6,294,108
location	3,088
measurement	3,387,775
note	0

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TABLERNAME	COUNT
observation	1,925,159
observation_period	104,891
payer_plan_period	389,231
person	116,352
procedure_occurrence	13,857,192
provider	631,920
specimen	0
visit_details	0

Query executed in 13.93 secs

Data density plots

Figure 1. Total record count over time per data domain

Figure 2. Number of records per person over time per data domain

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Concepts per person

Table 2. Shows the number of records per person for all data domains

Domain	Min	P10	P25	MEDIAN	P75	P90	Max
Condition era	1	8	38	85	136	188	353
Condition occurrence	1	8	38	86	138	190	357
Drug era	1	4	9	39	78	110	200
Drug exposure	1	5	9	41	87	128	241
Measurement	1	4	12	21	31	40	93
Observation	1	2	6	11	17	23	51
Procedure occurrence	1	7	34	68	103	136	245

VOCABULARY MAPPING

Describe how the vocabulary mapping process was implemented, and what the quality control mechanism are.

All the custom mappings need to be shared with the report as Excel file or as source_to_concept map, to allow for random checks by EHDEN's vocabulary team. Ideally these lists are sorted descending by source code frequency.

Vocabularies

Vocabulary version: v5.0 05-NOV-17

Table 3. The vocabularies available in the CDM with concept count

ID	NAME	VERSION	NUM_STANDA RD	NUM_CLASSIFICATI ON	NUM_NON_STAND ARD
ABMS	Provider Specialty (American Board of Medical Specialties)	NA	89	0	0
ATC	WHO Anatomic Therapeutic Chemical Classification	RxNorm Full 20170807	0	6,082	47
Cohort Type	OMOP Cohort Type	NA	0	0	1
Concept Class	OMOP Concept Class	NA	0	0	300
Condition Type	OMOP Condition Occurrence Type	NA	100	0	0
Cost Type	OMOP Cost Type	NA	3	0	0

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ID	NAME	VERSION	NUM_STANDA RD	NUM_CLASSIFICATI ON	NUM_NON_STAND ARD
CPT4	Current Procedural Terminology version 4 (AMA)	2017AA	10,524	3,262	1,660
Currency	International Currency Symbol (ISO 4217)	2008	180	0	0
Death Type	OMOP Death Type	NA	14	0	0
Device Type	OMOP Device Type	NA	3	0	0
Domain	OMOP Domain	NA	0	0	55
Drug Type	OMOP Drug Exposure Type	NA	14	0	0
Ethnicity	OMOP Ethnicity	NA	2	0	0
Gender	OMOP Gender	NA	2	0	3
HCPCS	Healthcare Common Procedure Coding System (CMS)	2017 Alpha Numeric HCPCS File	5,294	0	2,835
ICD10CM	International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision, Clinical Modification (NCHS)	ICD10CM FY2017 code descriptions	0	0	108,971
ICD9CM	International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Revision, Clinical Modification, Volume 1 and 2 (NCHS)	ICD9CM v32 master descriptions	0	0	18,672
ICD9Proc	International Classification of Diseases, Ninth Revision, Clinical Modification, Volume 3 (NCHS)	ICD9CM v32 master descriptions	4,651	0	6

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ID	NAME	VERSION	NUM_STANDA RD	NUM_CLASSIFICATI ON	NUM_NON_STAND ARD
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (Regenstrief Institute)	LOINC 2.61	93,220	38,458	4,221
Meas Type	OMOP Measurement Type	NA	6	0	0
NDC	National Drug Code (FDA and manufacturers)	NDC 20171023	0	0	769,530
NDFRT	National Drug File - Reference Terminology (VA)	RxNorm Full 20170807	0	18,542	18,869
None	OMOP Standardized Vocabularies	v5.0 05-NOV-17	0	0	1
Note Type	OMOP Note Type	NA	10	0	0
NUCC	National Uniform Claim Committee Health Care Provider Taxonomy Code Set (NUCC)	2013-07-01	829	0	0
Obs Period Type	OMOP Observation Period Type	NA	6	0	0
Observation Type	OMOP Observation Type	NA	13	0	0
Place of Service	Place of Service Codes for Professional Claims (CMS)	2009-01-11	59	0	0
Procedure Type	OMOP Procedure Occurrence Type	NA	95	0	0

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ID	NAME	VERSION	NUM_STANDA RD	NUM_CLASSIFICATI ON	NUM_NON_STAND ARD
Race	Race and Ethnicity Code Set (USBC)	Version 1.0	50	0	3
Relationship	OMOP Relationship	NA	12	0	416
Revenue Code	UB04/CMS145 0 Revenue Codes (CMS)	2010 Release	538	0	0
RxNorm	RxNorm (NLM)	RxNorm Full 20170807	146,228	37,172	95,169
RxNorm Extension	RxNorm Extension (OMOP)	RxNorm Extension 15-OCT-17	1,468,309	0	193,853
SNOMED	Systematic Nomenclature of Medicine - Clinical Terms (IHTSDO)	SnomedCT Release 20170401	331,235	0	454,477
Specialty	Medicare provider/supplier specialty codes (CMS)	NA	107	0	4
SPL	Structured Product Labeling (FDA)	NDC 20171023	0	224,583	14,854
UCUM	Unified Code for Units of Measure (Regenstrief Institute)	Version 1.8.2	883	0	89
VA Class	VA National Drug File Class (VA)	RxNorm Full 20170807	0	486	0
Visit	OMOP Visit	NA	5	0	0
Visit Type	OMOP Visit Type	NA	3	0	0
Vocabulary	OMOP Vocabulary	NA	0	0	82

Query executed in 5.09 secs

Table counts

Table 4. Shows the number of records in all vocabulary tables

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TABLERNAME	COUNT
concept	4,075,186
concept_ancestor	121,111,843
concept_class	300
concept_relationship	27,457,992
concept_synonym	5,491,313
domain	39
drug_strength	2,430,381
vocabulary	42

Query executed in 20.78 secs

Mapping Completeness

Table 5. Shows the percentage of codes that are mapped to the standardized vocabularies as well as the percentage of records.

Domain	#Codes Source	#Codes Mapped	%Codes Mapped	#Records Source	#Records Mapped	%Records Mapped
condition	10,313	10,292	99.80	14,803,406	14,775,949	99.81
procedure	8,607	8,018	93.16	13,857,192	13,246,809	95.60
device	811	760	93.71	224,499	222,163	98.96
drug	269,187	265,251	98.54	6,294,108	6,219,065	98.81
observation	1,759	1,612	91.64	1,925,159	1,765,558	91.71
measurement	998	955	95.69	3,387,775	3,358,281	99.13
visit_occurrence	5,579,542	844,593	15.14	5,579,542	844,593	15.14
measurement-unit	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
observation-unit	0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
measurement-value	1	0	0.00	3,387,775	0	0.00
observation-value	1	0	0.00	1,925,159	0	0.00

Query executed in 30.05 secs

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Drug Mappings

Table 6. The level of the drug mappings

CLASS	#RECORDS	#PATIENTS	#SOURCE CODES
Clinical Drug	4,402,549	100,478	215,778
Branded Drug	842,564	79,921	34,446
Quant Clinical Drug	186,097	59,496	9,088
Quant Branded Drug	133,461	53,189	5,444
Undefined	75,043	44,189	3,936
Ingredient	248,640	49,172	116
Clinical Drug Comp	192,172	45,198	104
Clinical Drug Form	47,409	28,118	93
HCPCS	62,084	22,791	81
CPT4	101,888	53,606	48
Clinical Pack	394	391	36
Branded Pack	167	167	12
Branded Drug Form	1,640	1,556	5

Query executed in 36.99 secs

Unmapped Codes

Table 7. Top 25 of unmapped drugs

ROW_NUM	SOURCE VALUE	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
1	G9141	6,200	5,900
2	J3487	2,100	2,000
3	G9142	1,100	1,000
4	J3488	900	800
5	90703	600	600
6	00047200820	200	200
7	00047200922	200	200
8	00047200920	200	200
9	00047200822	200	200
10	00703408511	100	100
11	17088266101	100	100
12	54087032518	100	100
13	40042001710	100	100
14	17088260601	100	100
15	17088260901	100	100
16	17088260101	100	100
17	00555119614	100	100
18	54087035618	100	100
19	58364119604	100	100
20	54087032618	100	100
21	15210040211	100	100
22	00083260901	100	100
23	J1785	100	100
24	17088009201	100	100

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<u>ROW_NUM</u>	<u>SOURCE VALUE</u>	<u>#RECORDS</u>	<u>#SUBJECTS</u>
25	00083260104	100	100

Query executed in 1.98 secs

Table 8. Top 25 of unmapped conditions

<u>ROW_NUM</u>	<u>SOURCE VALUE</u>	<u>#RECORDS</u>	<u>#SUBJECTS</u>
1	7395	13,700	10,200
2	7390	4,400	3,600
3	7396	3,100	3,000
4	7397	2,800	2,600
5	7398	2,600	2,500
6	32735	400	400
7	99559	200	200
8	99552	200	200
9	0770	200	200
10	37641	100	100
11	5226	100	100
12	1398	100	100
13	65583	100	100
14	65593	100	100
15	74446	100	100

Query executed in 0.43 secs

Table 9. Top 25 of unmapped measurements

<u>ROW_NUM</u>	<u>SOURCE VALUE</u>	<u>#RECORDS</u>	<u>#SUBJECTS</u>
1	80101	8,000	6,200
2	G0431	3,800	2,700
3	82055	2,800	2,600
4	83925	2,300	1,600
5	87621	1,900	1,800
6	80154	1,700	1,500
7	82145	1,400	1,100
8	80100	1,200	1,200
9	83840	1,100	800
10	80102	800	800
11	82205	800	600
12	82003	700	700
13	80196	700	700
14	82520	700	600
15	82491	600	600
16	83805	600	500
17	G0430	300	300
18	82492	300	200
19	82541	300	300
20	88347	200	200
21	82544	100	100

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ROW_NUM	SOURCE VALUE	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
22	82651	100	100
23	83887	100	100
24	80182	100	100
25	82980	100	100

Query executed in 0.61 secs

Table 10. Top 25 of unmapped observations

ROW_NUM	SOURCE VALUE	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
1	G8445	56,100	35,600
2	G8447	33,900	25,500
3	G8443	15,900	13,700
4	G8446	13,700	12,100
5	G8553	10,100	9,000
6	G8457	6,000	5,600
7	G8448	5,500	5,200
8	Q1003	5,300	4,700
9	G0317	3,600	1,100
10	G8440	1,300	1,200
11	G8429	1,000	1,000
12	M0064	900	900
13	G8470	500	500
14	G8455	500	500
15	G0323	400	400
16	V8905	400	400
17	G0319	400	300
18	G8590	400	400
19	V8909	300	300
20	G0327	300	100
21	G8593	300	300
22	G8437	300	300
23	V8901	300	300
24	G8588	300	300
25	G8449	300	300

Query executed in 0.90 secs

Table 11. Top 25 of unmapped procedures

ROW_NUM	SOURCE VALUE	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
1	77052	51,100	28,700
2	92135	42,500	26,700
3	90806	32,500	16,900
4	90862	28,900	17,700
5	97001	25,200	18,800
6	77057	20,600	16,000
7	73510	19,300	15,700
8	78478	15,400	10,000

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ROW_NUM	SOURCE VALUE	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
9	78480	15,200	10,000
10	90772	12,800	10,300
11	77418	12,400	6,800
12	78465	11,500	9,600
13	77051	9,300	7,200
14	62311	8,600	7,800
15	93545	8,600	6,400
16	93556	8,500	6,300
17	77413	8,500	4,700
18	90805	8,100	6,800
19	90801	8,100	7,000
20	90816	7,400	5,800
21	90818	7,400	5,900
22	76645	7,300	6,400
23	77414	7,200	4,300
24	93543	7,100	5,500
25	93555	6,900	5,300

Query executed in 3.08 secs

Table 12. Top 25 of unmapped devices

ROW_NUM	SOURCE VALUE	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
1	C1300	2,000	1,400
2	C1879	200	200
3	E0230	100	100
4	L1800	100	100
5	L1825	100	100
6	L3651	100	100
7	D1110	100	100

Query executed in 0.40 secs

Mapped Codes

Table 13. Top 25 of mapped drugs

ROW_NUM	CONCEPT NAME	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
1	Epoetin Alfa	139,300	9,500
2	""	101,900	53,700
3	paricalcitol 0.001 MG	75,800	2,800
4	Oxygen 99 % Gas for Inhalation	61,500	37,400
5	Gemfibrozil 600 MG Oral Tablet	37,700	27,000
6	Omeprazole 20 MG Delayed Release Oral Capsule	37,000	24,800
7	Lovastatin 20 MG Oral Tablet	32,100	24,100
8	Simvastatin 40 MG Oral Tablet	29,900	23,000
9	Simvastatin 20 MG Oral Tablet	27,900	21,600
10	Lovastatin 40 MG Oral Tablet	27,300	21,300
11	Furosemide 40 MG Oral Tablet	25,100	19,900

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ROW_NUM	CONCEPT NAME	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
12	Metformin hydrochloride 500 MG Oral Tablet	24,400	17,600
13	Hydrochlorothiazide 50 MG Oral Tablet	24,300	19,500
14	Injection, iron sucrose, 1 mg	24,100	3,300
15	Glyburide 5 MG Oral Tablet	23,300	17,100
16	Doxercalciferol 0.001 MG	23,000	2,300
17	Sodium Chloride Injectable Solution	22,900	16,800
18	Dipyridamole 25 MG Oral Tablet	22,700	15,500
19	Hydrochlorothiazide 25 MG Oral Tablet	22,100	18,000
20	Simvastatin 10 MG Oral Tablet	21,900	18,000
21	Lovastatin 10 MG Oral Tablet	21,500	17,800
22	Dipyridamole 50 MG Oral Tablet	21,100	14,700
23	Furosemide 20 MG Oral Tablet	21,000	17,200
24	Glipizide 10 MG Oral Tablet	20,000	15,300
25	Dipyridamole 75 MG Oral Tablet	19,800	14,000

Query executed in 16.77 secs

Table 14. Top 25 of mapped conditions

ROW_NUM	CONCEPT NAME	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
1	Type 2 diabetes mellitus	612,900	78,700
2	Atrial fibrillation	299,000	61,100
3	Chest pain	246,700	57,400
4	Pure hypercholesterolemia	224,500	67,700
5	Anemia	194,300	57,200
6	Coronary arteriosclerosis in native artery	184,100	53,400
7	Hypothyroidism	183,000	62,400
8	Malaise and fatigue	171,400	57,600
9	Congestive heart failure	166,500	51,700
10	Urinary tract infectious disease	164,100	54,100
11	Low back pain	154,900	52,300
12	Coronary arteriosclerosis	128,600	51,300
13	Dyspnea	118,100	46,300
14	Pain in limb	115,400	52,100
15	Abdominal pain	100,100	43,000
16	Type II diabetes mellitus uncontrolled	94,700	36,400
17	End stage renal disease	93,400	21,400
18	Actinic keratosis	85,700	33,600
19	Gastroesophageal reflux disease	83,600	47,200
20	Iron deficiency anemia	83,000	26,500
21	Onychomycosis due to dermatophyte	82,800	41,700
22	Nuclear senile cataract	80,600	37,900
23	Conduction disorder of the heart	75,100	36,900
24	Arthralgia of the lower leg	74,200	33,800
25	Respiratory symptom	72,700	35,000

Query executed in 22.38 secs

Table 15. Top 25 of mapped measurements

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ROW_NUM	CONCEPT NAME	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
1	""	3,290,600	91,900
2	Prostate cancer screening; prostate specific antigen test (psa)	16,900	15,000
3	Laboratory test	16,900	13,200
4	Screening cytopathology, cervical or vaginal (any reporting system), collected in preservative fluid, automated thin layer preparation, with screening by automated system and manual rescreening under physician supervision	5,600	5,300
5	Screening cytopathology, cervical or vaginal (any reporting system), collected in preservative fluid, automated thin layer preparation, screening by cytotechnologist under physician supervision	3,900	3,800
6	Immunology laboratory test	3,100	2,600
7	Colorectal cancer screening; fecal occult blood test, immunoassay, 1-3 simultaneous	3,100	3,000
8	Hematology screening test	2,600	2,500
9	Microscopic examination of vaginal Papanicolaou smear	2,500	2,500
10	Genetic test	2,500	2,400
11	Microscopic examination of cervical Papanicolaou smear	1,700	1,600
12	Blood group typing	1,600	1,600
13	Phenylketonuria screening test	1,200	1,200
14	Antenatal RhD antibody screening	1,200	1,200
15	Sickle cell disease screening test	1,200	1,200
16	Detection of parasite	800	800
17	Complete cbc, automated (hgb, hct, rbc, wbc, without platelet count) and automated wbc differential count	700	700
18	Screening papanicolaou smear, cervical or vaginal, up to three smears, by technician under physician supervision	600	600
19	Screening cytopathology, cervical or vaginal (any reporting system), collected in preservative fluid, automated thin layer preparation, requiring interpretation by physician	500	500
20	Complete (cbc), automated (hgb, hct, rbc, wbc; without platelet count)	400	400
21	Wet mounts, including preparations of vaginal, cervical or skin specimens	400	400
22	Type 1 hypersensitivity skin test	400	400
23	All potassium hydroxide (koh) preparations	200	200
24	Screening cytopathology, cervical or vaginal (any reporting system), collected in preservative fluid, automated thin layer preparation, with manual screening and rescreening by cytotechnologist under physician supervision	200	200
25	Screening cytopathology, cervical or vaginal (any reporting system), collected in preservative fluid, automated thin layer preparation, with screening by automated system, under physician supervision	100	100

Query executed in 8.72 secs

Table 16. Top 25 of mapped observations

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	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 35/48

ROW_NUM	CONCEPT NAME	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
1	Vaccination required	269,300	66,300
2	""	220,800	68,000
3	High risk drug monitoring status	184,900	53,100
4	History of clinical finding in subject	178,700	63,600
5	Ground mileage, per statute mile	82,600	34,700
6	Postoperative care	50,900	31,800
7	H/O: artificial joint	42,900	24,100
8	Ambulance service, basic life support, non-emergency transport, (bls)	38,300	23,200
9	Diabetic on insulin	34,100	25,300
10	Family history of clinical finding	31,800	24,900
11	Aftercare	30,700	21,700
12	Ambulance service, advanced life support, emergency transport, level 1 (als 1 - emergency)	29,700	22,500
13	H/O: artificial eye lens	27,200	19,800
14	Antineoplastic chemotherapy regimen	24,400	12,200
15	Low osmolar contrast material, 300-399 mg/ml iodine concentration, per ml	21,700	16,400
16	Abnormal weight loss	21,600	15,500
17	Cardiac pacemaker in situ	20,700	16,300
18	Dialysis finding	20,300	9,000
19	History of renal transplant	18,300	8,500
20	Ambulance service, basic life support, emergency transport (bls-emergency)	16,200	14,000
21	H/O: artificial heart valve	12,900	9,700
22	Fall	12,400	10,900
23	Follow-up encounter	12,300	10,600
24	H/O: surgery	10,800	9,400
25	Set-up portable x-ray equipment	10,400	8,500

Query executed in 4.87 secs

Table 17. Top 25 of mapped procedures

ROW_NUM	CONCEPT NAME	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
1	""	6,710,200	97,900
2	Other diagnostic procedures on lymphatic structures	658,600	84,500
3	Biopsy of lymphatic structure	517,300	81,300
4	Biopsy of mouth, unspecified structure	400,400	78,200
5	Long-term drug therapy	217,200	65,300
6	Excision of anus	137,000	51,800
7	Biopsy of uvula and soft palate	116,200	50,400
8	Screening for malignant neoplasm of breast	103,900	37,200
9	Incision of cervix to assist delivery	101,200	36,000
10	Surgical correction of prominent ear	98,800	23,800
11	Other resection of rectum	90,100	33,600
12	Administration of influenza virus vaccine	82,500	45,800
13	Bone graft, humerus	78,200	28,400
14	External version assisting delivery	74,600	30,800

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	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 36/48

ROW_NUM	CONCEPT NAME	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
15	Removal of implanted devices from bone, humerus	65,400	37,300
16	High forceps operation with episiotomy	65,200	32,500
17	Electrical stimulation (unattended), to one or more areas for indication(s) other than wound care, as part of a therapy plan of care	60,400	29,900
18	Other gastroenterostomy without gastrectomy	56,700	33,300
19	Application of external fixator device, humerus	55,700	27,500
20	Limb shortening procedures, radius and ulna	55,600	33,900
21	Temporary tracheostomy	52,800	32,400
22	Bone graft, carpals and metacarpals	52,200	31,200
23	Other and unspecified robotic assisted procedure	51,500	16,100
24	Other repair of urethra	51,000	23,900
25	Other diagnostic procedures on orbit and eyeball	46,800	14,500

Query executed in 27.22 secs

Table 18. Top 25 of mapped devices

ROW_NUM	CONCEPT NAME	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
1	Syringe, with or without needle, each	129,500	2,600
2	Non-covered item or service	15,400	12,500
3	Technetium tc-99m sestamibi, diagnostic, per study dose	7,100	6,000
4	Technetium tc-99m tetrofosmin, diagnostic, per study dose	5,400	4,700
5	Injection, gadolinium-based magnetic resonance contrast agent, not otherwise specified (nos), per ml	5,300	4,700
6	Miscellaneous dialysis supplies, not otherwise specified	5,300	1,300
7	Guide wire	4,300	4,000
8	Fluorodeoxyglucose f-18 fdg, diagnostic, per study dose, up to 45 millicuries	2,700	2,400
9	Thallium tl-201 thallos chloride, diagnostic, per millicurie	2,700	2,500
10	Introducer/sheath, other than guiding, other than intracardiac electrophysiological, non-laser	2,500	2,400
11	Surgical trays	2,400	2,300
12	Technetium tc-99m medronate, diagnostic, per study dose, up to 30 millicuries	2,000	1,700
13	Catheter, guiding (may include infusion/perfusion capability)	1,700	1,600
14	Catheter, transluminal angioplasty, non-laser (may include guidance, infusion/perfusion capability)	1,600	1,600
15	Closure device, vascular (implantable/insertable)	1,400	1,400
16	Catheter, infusion, inserted peripherally, centrally or midline (other than hemodialysis)	900	900
17	Gauze, non-impregnated, sterile, pad size 16 sq. in. or less, without adhesive border, each dressing	800	600
18	Posterior chamber intraocular lens	800	800
19	Lens, intraocular (new technology)	700	700
20	Gauze, non-impregnated, non-sterile, pad size 16 sq. in. or less, without adhesive border, each dressing	600	300
21	Mesh (implantable)	600	600
22	Catheter, drainage	600	600

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ROW_NUM	CONCEPT NAME	#RECORDS	#SUBJECTS
23	Anchor/screw for opposing bone-to-bone or soft tissue-to-bone (implantable)	500	500
24	Technetium tc-99m sulfur colloid, diagnostic, per study dose, up to 20 millicuries	500	500
25	Surgical supply; miscellaneous	500	500

Query executed in 1.13 secs

Source to concept map

If you did not use the source_to_concept_map table in the ETL the table below will be empty. In that case provide your custom mappings in an Excel file.

Table 19. Source to concept map breakdown

SOURCE_VOCABULARY_ID	TARGET_VOCABULARY_ID	COUNT
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Query executed in 0.37 secs

Note that the full source_to_concept_map table is added in the results.zip

TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Check that the following tools are available and functional: ATLAS, ACHILLES report. Functionality needs to be tested by design of cohort in Atlas, generation of cohort counts in ATLAS, execution of a simple cohort characterisation in ATLAS.

Is the data source added in the EHDEN Database Catalogue and has the CatalogUeExport results been uploaded for the visualizations? Also describe if a process has been agreed for updating this information regularly.

Add additional relevant information about the local infrastructure here, such as backup facilities, specifications webserver hosting ATLAS, testing environment if available etc.

CDM Source Table

Table 20. cdm_source table content

field	1
CDM_SOURCE_NAME	synpuf
CDM_SOURCE_ABBREVIATION	NA
CDM HOLDER	NA
SOURCE_DESCRIPTION	NA
SOURCE_DOCUMENTATION_REFERENCE	
CDM_ETL_REFERENCE	NA
SOURCE_RELEASE_DATE	2020-12-07
CDM_RELEASE_DATE	NA
CDM_VERSION	5.3.1
VOCABULARY_VERSION	NA

EHDEN <small>EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK</small>	D5.2 – Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures		
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	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 38/48

HADES packages

Table 21. Versions of all installed HADES R packages

Package	Version
Andromeda	0.4.0
CohortDiagnostics	2.0.0
CohortMethod	4.0.0
Cyclops	3.1.0
DatabaseConnector	3.0.0
DatabaseConnectorJars	1.1.0
EmpiricalCalibration	2.0.2
Eunomia	1.0.1
EvidenceSynthesis	0.2.0
FeatureExtraction	3.1.0
Hydra	0.1.0
MethodEvaluation	2.0.0
OhdsiSharing	0.2.2
ParallelLogger	2.0.1
PatientLevelPrediction	4.1.0
ROhdsiWebApi	1.1.2
SelfControlledCaseSeries	2.0.0
SelfControlledCohort	1.5.0
SqlRender	1.6.8

All HADES packages were available

System Information

Installed R version: R version 4.0.3 (2020-10-10)

System CPU vendor: GenuineIntel

System CPU model: Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-9880H CPU @ 2.30GHz

System CPU number of cores: 16

System RAM: 34.36 GB

DBMS: sql server

WebAPI version: 2.7.7

Vocabulary Query Performance

The number of 'Maps To' relations is equal to 3106724. This query was executed in 11.64 secs

Achilles Query Performance

Table 22. Execution time of queries of the Achilles R-Package

	D5.2 – Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures		
	WP5 – Data Workflow Implementation & Service Deployment		Version: v1.1 – Final
	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 39/48

ID	NAME	DURATION
0	Source name	0.091678 secs
1	Number of persons	0.041696 secs
2	Number of persons by gender	0.183182 secs
3	Number of persons by year of birth	0.058228 secs
4	Number of persons by race	0.059089 secs
5	Number of persons by ethnicity	0.070693 secs
7	Number of persons with invalid provider_id	0.056060 secs
8	Number of persons with invalid location_id	0.096566 secs
9	Number of persons with invalid care_site_id	0.054500 secs
10	Number of all persons by year of birth by gender	0.072196 secs
11	Number of non-deceased persons by year of birth by gender	0.099605 secs
12	Number of persons by race and ethnicity	0.077321 secs
101	Number of persons by age, with age at first observation period	0.176635 secs
102	Number of persons by gender by age, with age at first observation period	0.159337 secs
108	Number of persons by length of observation period, in 30d increments	0.217217 secs
109	Number of persons with continuous observation in each year	0.795322 secs
110	Number of persons with continuous observation in each month	10.731043 secs
111	Number of persons by observation period start month	0.216336 secs
112	Number of persons by observation period end month	0.157835 secs
113	Number of persons by number of observation periods	0.074423 secs
114	Number of persons with observation period before year-of-birth	0.126115 secs
115	Number of persons with observation period end < observation period start	0.056148 secs
116	Number of persons with at least one day of observation in each year by gender and age decile	1.783371 secs
117	Number of persons with at least one day of observation in each month	11.326960 secs

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	WP5 – Data Workflow Implementation & Service Deployment		Version: v1.1 – Final
	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 40/48

ID	NAME	DURATION
118	Number of observation periods with invalid person_id	0.082853 secs
119	Number of observation period records by period_type_concept_id	0.056829 secs
200	Number of persons with at least one visit occurrence, by visit_concept_id	2.925766 secs
201	Number of visit occurrence records, by visit_concept_id	2.710461 secs
202	Number of persons by visit occurrence start month, by visit_concept_id	5.914636 secs
204	Number of persons with at least one visit occurrence, by visit_concept_id by calendar year by gender by age decile	5.323025 secs
207	Number of visit records with invalid person_id	1.546856 secs
208	Number of visit records outside valid observation period	2.198143 secs
209	Number of visit records with end date < start date	0.513847 secs
210	Number of visit records with invalid care_site_id	2.045144 secs
212	Number of persons with at least one visit occurrence, by calendar year by gender by age decile	4.888385 secs
220	Number of visit occurrence records by visit occurrence start month	3.809848 secs
221	Number of persons by visit start year	3.359340 secs
225	Number of visit_occurrence records by visit_source_concept_id	1.327818 secs
300	Number of providers	0.144437 secs
301	Number of providers by specialty concept_id	1.195023 secs
302	Number of providers with invalid care site id	0.330636 secs
325	Number of provider records by specialty_source_concept_id	0.168504 secs
400	Number of persons with at least one condition occurrence, by condition_concept_id	5.380062 secs
401	Number of condition occurrence records, by condition_concept_id	2.679631 secs
402	Number of persons by condition occurrence start month, by condition_concept_id	18.999160 secs
404	Number of persons with at least one condition occurrence, by condition_concept_id by calendar year by gender by age decile	20.714319 secs
405	Number of condition occurrence records, by condition_concept_id by condition_type_concept_id	5.871664 secs
409	Number of condition occurrence records with invalid person_id	4.036531 secs

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	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 41/48

ID	NAME	DURATION
410	Number of condition occurrence records outside valid observation period	6.051113 secs
411	Number of condition occurrence records with end date < start date	2.057181 secs
412	Number of condition occurrence records with invalid provider_id	5.043638 secs
413	Number of condition occurrence records with invalid visit_id	7.481834 secs
420	Number of condition occurrence records by condition occurrence start month	10.181705 secs
424	Number of co-occurring condition_occurrence condition_concept_id pairs	2.300317 hours
425	Number of condition_occurrence records by condition_source_concept_id	5.263985 secs
500	Number of persons with death, by cause_concept_id	0.033817 secs
501	Number of records of death, by cause_concept_id	0.023165 secs
502	Number of persons by death month	0.067278 secs
504	Number of persons with a death, by calendar year by gender by age decile	0.071771 secs
505	Number of death records, by death_type_concept_id	0.030138 secs
509	Number of death records with invalid person_id	0.049869 secs
510	Number of death records outside valid observation period	0.055249 secs
525	Number of death records by cause_source_concept_id	0.026784 secs
600	Number of persons with at least one procedure occurrence, by procedure_concept_id	5.108358 secs
601	Number of procedure occurrence records, by procedure_concept_id	2.324662 secs
602	Number of persons by procedure occurrence start month, by procedure_concept_id	16.993680 secs
604	Number of persons with at least one procedure occurrence, by procedure_concept_id by calendar year by gender by age decile	17.071125 secs
605	Number of procedure occurrence records, by procedure_concept_id by procedure_type_concept_id	4.307118 secs
609	Number of procedure occurrence records with invalid person_id	3.295144 secs
610	Number of procedure occurrence records outside valid observation period	5.463451 secs
612	Number of procedure occurrence records with invalid provider_id	4.679316 secs
613	Number of procedure occurrence records with invalid visit_id	6.219301 secs

	D5.2 – Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures		
	WP5 – Data Workflow Implementation & Service Deployment		Version: v1.1 – Final
	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 42/48

ID	NAME	DURATION
620	Number of procedure occurrence records by procedure occurrence start month	8.760135 secs
624	Number of co-occurring procedure_occurrence procedure_concept_id pairs	55.061515 mins
625	Number of procedure_occurrence records by procedure_source_concept_id	4.217861 secs
691	Percentage of total persons that have at least x procedures	6.357057 secs
700	Number of persons with at least one drug exposure, by drug_concept_id	3.079393 secs
701	Number of drug exposure records, by drug_concept_id	1.134527 secs
702	Number of persons by drug exposure start month, by drug_concept_id	11.885105 secs
704	Number of persons with at least one drug exposure, by drug_concept_id by calendar year by gender by age decile	9.699256 secs
705	Number of drug exposure records, by drug_concept_id by drug_type_concept_id	2.715549 secs
709	Number of drug exposure records with invalid person_id	1.611035 secs
710	Number of drug exposure records outside valid observation period	2.323260 secs
711	Number of drug exposure records with end date < start date	1.095796 secs
712	Number of drug exposure records with invalid provider_id	1.582338 secs
713	Number of drug exposure records with invalid visit_id	1.500728 secs
720	Number of drug exposure records by drug exposure start month	4.051641 secs
724	Number of co-occurring drug_exposure drug_concept_id pairs	1.010575 hours
725	Number of drug_exposure records by drug_source_concept_id	4.621935 secs
791	Percentage of total persons that have at least x drug exposures	4.312996 secs
800	Number of persons with at least one observation occurrence, by observation_concept_id	0.702413 secs
801	Number of observation occurrence records, by observation_concept_id	0.364348 secs
802	Number of persons by observation occurrence start month, by observation_concept_id	2.353778 secs
804	Number of persons with at least one observation occurrence, by observation_concept_id by calendar year by gender by age decile	2.399461 secs
805	Number of observation occurrence records, by observation_concept_id by observation_type_concept_id	0.548361 secs
807	Number of observation occurrence records, by observation_concept_id and unit_concept_id	0.542313 secs

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	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 43/48

ID	NAME	DURATION
809	Number of observation records with invalid person_id	0.525063 secs
810	Number of observation records outside valid observation period	0.753375 secs
812	Number of observation records with invalid provider_id	0.947995 secs
813	Number of observation records with invalid visit_id	2.219671 secs
814	Number of observation records with no value (numeric, string, or concept)	0.193324 secs
820	Number of observation records by observation start month	1.674066 secs
822	Number of observation records, by observation_concept_id and value_as_concept_id	0.687462 secs
823	Number of observation records, by observation_concept_id and qualifier_concept_id	0.621082 secs
824	Number of co-occurring observation observation_concept_id pairs	43.725993 secs
825	Number of observation records by observation_source_concept_id	0.488202 secs
826	Number of observation records by value_as_concept_id	0.484036 secs
827	Number of observation records by unit_concept_id	0.404343 secs
891	Percentage of total persons that have at least x observations	1.212092 secs
900	Number of persons with at least one drug era, by drug_concept_id	2.448727 secs
901	Number of drug era records, by drug_concept_id	1.043789 secs
902	Number of persons by drug era start month, by drug_concept_id	9.515116 secs
904	Number of persons with at least one drug era, by drug_concept_id by calendar year by gender by age decile	9.251103 secs
908	Number of drug eras without valid person	1.686578 secs
909	Number of drug eras outside valid observation period	2.768495 secs
910	Number of drug eras with end date < start date	0.655557 secs
920	Number of drug era records by drug era start month	4.186234 secs
1,000	Number of persons with at least one condition era, by condition_concept_id	4.415717 secs
1,001	Number of condition era records, by condition_concept_id	1.921693 secs
1,002	Number of persons by condition era start month, by condition_concept_id	15.667716 secs

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	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 44/48

ID	NAME	DURATION
1,004	Number of persons with at least one condition era, by condition_concept_id by calendar year by gender by age decile	15.305212 secs
1,008	Number of condition eras without valid person	2.640580 secs
1,009	Number of condition eras outside valid observation period	3.393941 secs
1,010	Number of condition eras with end date < start date	0.854347 secs
1,020	Number of condition era records by condition era start month	6.440133 secs
1,100	Number of persons by location 3-digit zip	0.053521 secs
1,101	Number of persons by location state	0.077448 secs
1,102	Number of care sites by location 3-digit zip	0.119123 secs
1,103	Number of care sites by location state	0.069172 secs
1,200	Number of persons by place of service	0.043172 secs
1,201	Number of visits by place of service	2.278594 secs
1,202	Number of care sites by place of service	0.139674 secs
1,203	Number of visits by place of service discharge type	0.438741 secs
1,408	Number of persons by length of payer plan period, in 30d increments	0.715718 secs
1,409	Number of persons with continuous payer plan in each year	3.582449 secs
1,410	Number of persons with continuous payer plan in each month	7.786993 secs
1,411	Number of persons by payer plan period start month	0.432426 secs
1,412	Number of persons by payer plan period end month	0.487946 secs
1,413	Number of persons by number of payer plan periods	0.180353 secs
1,414	Number of persons with payer plan period before year-of-birth	0.245990 secs
1,415	Number of persons with payer plan period end < payer plan period start	0.088444 secs
1,800	Number of persons with at least one measurement occurrence, by measurement_concept_id	1.195491 secs
1,801	Number of measurement occurrence records, by measurement_concept_id	0.506576 secs
1,802	Number of persons by measurement occurrence start month, by measurement_concept_id	4.277425 secs

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	WP5 – Data Workflow Implementation & Service Deployment		Version: v1.1 – Final
	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 45/48

ID	NAME	DURATION
1,804	Number of persons with at least one measurement occurrence, by measurement_concept_id by calendar year by gender by age decile	4.519690 secs
1,805	Number of measurement occurrence records, by measurement_concept_id by measurement_type_concept_id	0.957127 secs
1,807	Number of measurement occurrence records, by measurement_concept_id and unit_concept_id	0.953142 secs
1,809	Number of measurement records with invalid person_id	0.920115 secs
1,810	Number of measurement records outside valid observation period	1.362185 secs
1,812	Number of measurement records with invalid provider_id	1.399858 secs
1,813	Number of measurement records with invalid visit_id	3.019805 secs
1,814	Number of measurement records with no value (numeric, string, or concept)	0.319466 secs
1,818	Number of measurement records below/within/above normal range, by measurement_concept_id and unit_concept_id	0.420035 secs
1,820	Number of measurement records by measurement start month	1.419406 secs
1,821	Number of measurement records with no numeric value	0.488336 secs
1,822	Number of measurement records, by measurement_concept_id and value_as_concept_id	0.811626 secs
1,823	Number of measurement records, by measurement_concept_id and operator_concept_id	0.921060 secs
1,824	Number of co-occurring measurement measurement_concept_id pairs	3.858810 mins
1,825	Number of measurement records by measurement_source_concept_id	0.831013 secs
1,826	Number of measurement records by value_as_concept_id	0.894655 secs
1,827	Number of measurement records by unit_concept_id	0.921372 secs
1,891	Percentage of total persons that have at least x measurements	1.705694 secs
1,900	Source values mapped to concept_id 0 by table, by source_value	8.943530 secs
2,000	Number of patients with at least 1 Dx and 1 Rx	4.858068 secs
2,001	Number of patients with at least 1 Dx and 1 Proc	5.085122 secs
2,002	Number of patients with at least 1 Meas, 1 Dx and 1 Rx	1.501264 secs
2,003	Number of patients with at least 1 Visit	1.083741 secs
2,100	Number of persons with at least one device exposure, by device_concept_id	0.129376 secs

	D5.2 – Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures		
	WP5 – Data Workflow Implementation & Service Deployment		Version: v1.1 – Final
	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 46/48

ID	NAME	DURATION
2,101	Number of device exposure records, by device_concept_id	0.071823 secs
2,102	Number of persons by device records start month, by device_concept_id	0.236976 secs
2,104	Number of persons with at least one device exposure, by device_concept_id by calendar year by gender by age decile	0.313716 secs
2,105	Number of device exposure records, by device_concept_id by device_type_concept_id	0.111327 secs
2,125	Number of device_exposure records by device_source_concept_id	0.096454 secs
2,200	Number of persons with at least one note by note_type_concept_id	0.036714 secs
2,201	Number of note records, by note_type_concept_id	0.020697 secs

Query executed in 0.67 secs

SCIENTIFIC PREPAREDNESS

This section contains several items related to the interaction with the EHDEN/OHDSI community and training after the mapping process.

Staff training

Describe how the Data Partner will train and educate the different users of the system in their organization and what the current status is of the expertise in the team.

Study execution

Describe how the Data Partner will be able to execute the ongoing OHDSI/EHDEN network studies, e.g. are there governance issues, lack of resources, etc.

Are there plans to initiate research studies?

Are there plans to participate in OHDSI Working Groups?

QUALITY CONTROL

Show that the Data Quality Dashboard results are 100% and check if the thresholds have been changed by doing a diff with the default.

Discuss with the Data Partner why the thresholds have been changed and share this information.

Have the Achilles results been reviewed by the Data Partner?

How is the ETL code tested? Discuss the quality controls steps or ideally share the code that executes this. Have all checks been passed? For example, is there a comparison available of the person count on the source and CDM and are the differences explained?

MAINTENANCE

	D5.2 – Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures		
	WP5 – Data Workflow Implementation & Service Deployment		Version: v1.1 – Final
	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU 47/48

Describe briefly the process the Data Partner implemented to keep the data in the OMOP CDM up-to-date when new source data will become available, if the local coding systems are updated, or if new versions of the CDM will be released. Describe how versions of the CDM will be maintained over time.

Describe the maintenance process put in place by the data partner for the tool updates.

EHDEN <small>EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK</small>	D5.2 – Report on Quality Assurance and Control Procedures		
	WP5 – Data Workflow Implementation & Service Deployment		Version: v1.1 – Final
	Author(s): Clair Blacketer, Michael Kallfelz, Peter Rijnbeek		Security: PU

CHECKLIST

Have the following checks been performed?

ATLAS cohort creation, e.g. Type 2 Diabetes

Check of Achilles results

Comments:

Check that all the items mentioned below are shared with EHDEN in addition to this inspection report. If items cannot be shared, add an explanation in the comments section.

ETL Documentation

ETL Code

DQD dashboard json file

White Rabbit output

CdmInspection results.zip

Comments: